

Accelerating additive manufacturing simulations using dynamic mode decomposition reduced-order models

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Abstract

We accelerate thermal simulations of the directed energy deposition (DED) additive manufacturing process using dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) reduced order model (ROM) and achieve a speedup of 1.3×10^6 while maintaining a worst-case error of under 10% when doing parametric interpolation. DMD is used in different ways to accelerate full-order model simulation results: first, we showcase its ability to compress and faithfully reproduce single track and multi-layer simulations; second, we introduce windowed DMD and parametric DMD to predict high-fidelity continuum, i.e. full-order model (FOM), results for different model parameters and for multi-layer simulations. Parametric DMD is realized through manifold projection and radial basis function interpolation over a convex domain of parameter values. For multi-layer simulations, parameters include initial conditions, which are compressed through a proper orthogonal decomposition of FOM results. The continuum simulations incorporate data from both experimentation and high-fidelity hydrodynamic simulations of the additive manufacturing processes to provide a more complete picture of the simulation parameters and boundary conditions present. The simulation results show good agreement between the reduced order model DMD prediction and the FOM in both predicted thermal results and in microstructure predictions.

Keywords: additive manufacturing; directed energy deposition; dynamic mode decomposition; reduced order modeling

1. Introduction

Simulations of the additive manufacturing process are useful to gain fundamental physical understanding and optimize the process parameter space [1-3]. These simulations can explain regimes of laser melting (conduction to keyhole transition) [4-6] and the complex transition from stable to unstable keyhole melt flow [7, 8], provide insight into the formation of defects and spattering [9-11], and describe microstructural features and mechanical properties of a built part [12]. Beyond understanding the deposition process, simulations help with parameter optimization which plays a role in component qualification [13].

These high-fidelity simulations are computationally expensive, making it impractical to scale these techniques to the part level. Part level simulations have been accomplished using lower fidelity continuum models, which do not explicitly model powder particles and the melt flow, opting to treat deposited material as a block of material periodically inserted into the simulation [2, 14]. This precludes capturing inclusions and potential defects that may occur during the manufacturing process but speeds up simulation considerably. However, even at the continuum modeling scale, the simulation process is long, which makes it difficult to complete parametric studies to optimize process parameters.

To speed up the prediction process, analytical solutions have been developed which bypass the simulation process entirely, such as the thermal model by Eagar and Tsai [15], which gives the solution of a moving, distributed heating source. The generalized solution is given by a Green's function which can be integrated to give a thermal profile. These techniques have delivered accurate results after appropriate calibration. Owing to the success of these methods and their utility, they remain an active area of research to this day [16-19]. However, employing an analytical model for the prediction of the additive manufacturing process sacrifices the generality in domain definition and application of boundary conditions that simulation using the finite element method provides. This is particularly an issue when moving to part-scale models and multi-track simulations with complex toolpath and irregular domains and complicated initial conditions.

Recently, interest in machine learning (ML) and data-driven methods has exploded as a means to generate predictive output given some input criteria. These ideas have also found a home in the realm of additive manufacturing. The applications to additive manufacturing are numerous, from simply using a trained model to predict quantities of interest, such as melt pool size, material properties, or defect locations in near real-time, to applying distortion compensation to a printed part such that the cooled part matches some desired shape [20], to predicting full simulation results given parameter values and initial conditions. While they have been successfully applied, one caveat of

applying ML techniques is their lack of interpretability: the models act as a black box and can give non-physical predictions, the cause of which can be difficult to pin down. Using data-driven techniques to predict simulation results provides more generality at the expense of potentially increasing the amount of data needed to represent the underlying model.

The focus of this work is on model order reduction, or reduced order modeling (ROM). These methods capture underlying patterns that simplify the representation of complex physics dynamics. We review some successful reduced order modeling work, such as in Dong et al. [21], on distortion compensation that skips the expensive iterative search for pre-compensated geometry by learning the fundamental modes of deformation using a principal component analysis-based ROM and trains a Gaussian process over the discovered modes to perform very fast prediction of compensated geometry and achieves good results for new, unseen geometries. In Favoretto et al. [22], another ROM based on proper generalized decomposition captures (in two dimensions) the transient non-linear thermal physics in laser powder bed fusion, while accounting for phase changes and material non-linearities. In Yan et al. [23], a reduced order model called self-consistent clustering analysis for mechanical modeling based on a computational homogenization approach accounts for microstructure at the macroscale indirectly by using k-means classification method. Also, some promising new graph theoretic approaches have been implemented [24-26] and these are deployed to print full-scale parts, as they capture the evolution of the thermal field and enable process optimization.

Here, we focus on dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) ROM. Introduced by Schmid [27], DMD approximates the evolving dynamics of the given data via a linear operator, which is compressed using singular value decomposition (SVD). A benefit of DMD-based ROMs is their amenability to enhancements, such as the addition of control parameters, both dynamic [28] and static [29], and randomized DMD [30] for reducing the size of snapshot data.

We developed DMD ROM for a continuum directed energy deposition (DED) model and cover the challenges to make the prediction error metric as low as possible for transient, non-linear 3D physics. DED is a popular additive manufacturing technique where metal powder is fed through a nozzle that houses a co-axial laser. The laser heats the substrate, as well as the falling powder, and generates a melt pool, causing material to build up from the base plate. There are many process parameters which control the quality of the subsequent built part in DED, but we focus on laser power and scan speed. We show that the DMD can be used to significantly speed a basic model which begins from additive manufacturing process parameters and a tool path and ends with microstructure predictions for the part based on cellular automaton simulation [12]. In this workflow, determining the thermal profile takes a large portion of the total computer runtime, so speeding up this component is an important part of realizing near real-time microstructure predictions.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the details of the DMD algorithm are covered, with extensions for windowed DMD and parametric DMD discussed in Appendix A. Section 3 introduces the salient parts of the workflow, including the continuum model itself and its coupling to the cellular automata simulation. In Section 4, we describe numerical examples which demonstrate DMD as a capable tool for prediction of parameter values which are not included in the training data set. We conclude in Section 5 with a summary of our results.

2. Theory and methods: dynamic mode decomposition

Dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) is a data-driven technique used in the field of applied mathematics and data analysis. It is primarily applied to analyze and extract coherent structures or patterns from time-varying data, such as time series, sensor measurements, or simulations. DMD provides a way to decompose complex, high-dimensional datasets into simpler components that capture the dominant temporal behaviors and spatial patterns. The methods described below are implemented in libROM, an open source library for model order reduction techniques and physics informed data driven methods [31]. This section provides a brief description of the DMD algorithm, though several enhancements are needed to produce an accurate, parametric DMD of the DED continuum model. These enhancements, namely windowed DMD and parametric interpolation, are covered in Appendix A.

2.1. Description of the algorithm

DMD begins with a dataset that represents a dynamic system's behavior over time. This dataset can be in the form of snapshots, which can be measurements or simulation results taken at equally spaced time intervals, Δt . With DMD, the number of snapshot degrees of freedom, M , is assumed to be much larger than the number of snapshots in time, N . The data is organized into an $M \times N$ data matrix,

$$\mathbf{U} = [\mathbf{u}_1 \quad \mathbf{u}_2 \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{u}_{N-1} \quad \mathbf{u}_N], \quad (1)$$

where each column $\mathbf{u}_i \in \mathbb{R}^M$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$ corresponds to a snapshot in time, and each row corresponds to a specific variable or observation within each snapshot. The snapshots are then subdivided into two different $M \times (N - 1)$ matrices:

$$\mathbf{U}^- = [\mathbf{u}_1 \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{u}_{N-1}] \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{U}^+ = [\mathbf{u}_2 \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{u}_N], \quad (2)$$

with the goal of determining the best linear operator \mathbf{A} such that $\mathbf{U}^+ \approx \mathbf{A}\mathbf{U}^-$, where best is defined as the operator which minimizes

$$\|\mathbf{U}^+ - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{U}^-\|_F, \quad (3)$$

where $\|\mathbf{X}\|_F$ denotes the Frobenius norm of \mathbf{X} . Note, this implies the dynamical evolution of the system can be described, or at least approximated, by a linear operator. The operator \mathbf{A} can be determined analytically by taking the Moore-Penrose pseudoinverse of \mathbf{U}^- , which is computed in the DMD using the singular value decomposition (SVD) to factorize \mathbf{U}^- :

$$\mathbf{U}^- = \overline{\mathbf{W}}\overline{\Sigma}\overline{\mathbf{V}}^T, \quad (4)$$

where $\overline{\mathbf{W}} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$ contains the left singular vectors, $\overline{\Sigma}$ is an $N \times N$ diagonal matrix containing the (real) singular values, and $\overline{\mathbf{V}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ holds right singular vectors. The left singular vectors $\overline{\mathbf{W}}$ are used to define DMD modes, which represent spatial patterns or structures within the data. The right singular vectors $\overline{\mathbf{V}}$ define the dynamics or temporal evolution of these modes. The singular values in $\overline{\Sigma}$ provide information about the importance of each mode.

The rank of the data matrix is reduced by retaining only the most significant singular values and their corresponding columns from $\overline{\mathbf{W}}$ and $\overline{\mathbf{V}}$. This step reduces the dimensionality of the problem and can eliminate noise. The amount of reduction is determined through the application of an *energy criterion*, which ensures a prescribed fraction of the total sum of the singular values is captured. Explicitly, the number of the singular values and modes retained is the smallest integer r which satisfies

Fig. 1. Overview of the dynamic mode decomposition algorithm.

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^r \Sigma_{ii}}{\sum_{i=1}^N \Sigma_{ii}} \geq \text{energy criterion}, \quad (5)$$

where Σ_{ii} represents the i th diagonal value of the matrix $\bar{\Sigma}$. Thus, the reduced SVD is

$$\mathbf{U}^- \approx \mathbf{W}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^T, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times r}$ is an orthogonal matrix which contains basis vectors for the r modes retained in the reduced representation, $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is a diagonal $r \times r$ matrix holding the r largest singular values, and $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times r}$ holds the r right singular vectors corresponding to the r singular values retained. With the reduced SVD, the linear operator \mathbf{A} is approximated as

$$\mathbf{A} \approx \mathbf{U}^+ \mathbf{V} \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1} \mathbf{W}^T. \quad (7)$$

The matrix \mathbf{A} can be represented in the reduced space by applying \mathbf{W}^T and \mathbf{W} to the left and right, respectively:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{U}^+ \mathbf{V} \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1} \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{U}^+ \mathbf{V} \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}. \quad (8)$$

Note $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ gives the dynamics of the snapshots projected into the reduced space:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{i+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i, \quad (9)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{u}_i$.

To simplify prediction using DMD, the eigenmodes of the reduced linear operator $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ can be utilized to give

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{X} \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{X}^{-1}, \quad (10)$$

where the columns of $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{r \times r}$ are the eigenvectors of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ and $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ is a diagonal $r \times r$ matrix whose entries are the (complex) eigenvalues of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$. Now, prediction at time t is given by

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{W} \mathbf{X} \mathbf{\Lambda}^{\frac{t}{\Delta t}} \mathbf{X}^{-1} \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{u}_1 = \mathbf{\Phi} \mathbf{\Lambda}^{\frac{t}{\Delta t}} \mathbf{b}_0, \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{\Phi} = \mathbf{W} \mathbf{X}$ and $\mathbf{b}_0 = \mathbf{\Phi}^* \mathbf{u}_1$. A summary of the DMD algorithm is illustrated in Figure 1.

One of the advantages of DMD is its amenability to enhancement of the framework. Numerous extensions have been proposed which have led to significant enhancements in the application and efficiency of DMD. Two enhancements we have applied to our usage of DMD include the time-windowing approach, introduced in Cheung et al. [32] and the parametric interpolation scheme devised in Choi et al. [33]. These enhancements are described in Appendix A.

3. Continuum model of the additive manufacturing processes

To build understanding of the DMD as applied to additive manufacturing simulations, we begin by exploring single track continuum modeling on the directed energy deposition (DED) additive manufacturing process, then build up to a multi-layer model. The details of this model are described in this section. For all simulations, the goal is to capture the temperature field in the substrate and the built-up layers as laser heating and melting occurs. This temperature field can then be used to determine the grain structure of the substrate and of the additively manufactured layers. As laser energy is introduced, the temperature evolution over the domain is governed by the heat initial value problem, the details of which are given in Section 3.1 below.

All simulations are modeled using the implicit thermal solver in ALE3D, a multiphysics arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian finite element code developed at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory [34]. For every simulation, the modeling domain includes both the substrate and the void region above it. This domain remains constant throughout the simulation. The material composition of each element in the domain is tracked through volume fraction fields of

each material present in the simulation. As a result, the addition of additively manufactured material into the simulation is greatly simplified, by evolving the volume fraction fields in each element. The tradeoff for this simplification is material interfaces do not conform to the mesh, which limits theoretical rates of convergence [35]. However, considering the complexities of evolving the mesh when new material is introduced, we deem the tradeoff to be acceptable. The rate and location of material introduction is assumed known *a priori* and is based on process parameters obtained from simulations and experiments (see Section 3.2).

3.1. Initial value problem for the heat equation

Given a computational domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ with boundary $\partial\Omega = \Gamma$ and a time range $[0, t_f] \subset \mathbb{R}$, the strong form of the heat equation is

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t}(\mathbf{x}, t)c(\mathbf{x}, t)\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}, t) = r(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega, t \in [0, t_f], \quad (12)$$

where $T(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the temperature field, $c(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the specific heat of the material, $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the material density, $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the heat flux vector field, and $r(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is a heat source term. Time dependence of the specific heat and density of the material are implicit through their dependence on temperature. Heat flux is linearly related to the temperature gradient through Fourier's law, which is

$$\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\mathbf{k}(\mathbf{x}, t)\nabla T(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{k}(\mathbf{x}, t) \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the heat conductivity matrix. The addition of boundary conditions and initial conditions on the problem complete the definition of the strong form:

$$\begin{aligned} T(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \bar{T}(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_T \subset \Gamma, t \in [0, t_f], \\ \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \mathbf{n} &= \bar{q}(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_q \subset \Gamma, t \in [0, t_f], \\ T(\mathbf{x}, 0) &= T_0(\mathbf{x}) \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The weak form follows from the strong form through the integration of (12) multiplied by a test function. Application of the divergence theorem and the inclusion of boundary conditions complete the weak formulation. Finite element approximations are introduced for the test function and the trial (temperature) field to complete the formulation of the semi-discrete equations of thermal diffusion. Time evolution of the resulting first order ordinary differential equation is accomplished by the introduction of a generalized midpoint rule.

3.2. Directed energy deposition continuum model

Directed energy deposition (DED) is an additive manufacturing technology where metal powder is fed through a nozzle which also holds a laser. The laser heats the substrate, as well as the powder that has exited the nozzle, giving a region of melted material underneath the laser called the melt pool. The falling powder gets entrained in the melt pool and builds up material from the substrate. The nozzle is held still while the part itself is connected to an articulated arm, giving great flexibility in where material is deposited. There are many parameters that control the subsequent built part, but the two we will focus on using the parametric DMD are laser scan speed (or velocity) and laser power. While these parameters can be tuned using experimentation, high-fidelity simulation also provides insight into the effects of varying machine parameters and can help guide the process of building parts with better characteristics, such as fewer pores and cracks and more equiaxed grains. Figure 2a illustrates the components of the high-fidelity simulation. First, powder travel through the nozzle is modelled with a discrete element method simulation. After the powder exits the nozzle but before it reaches the substrate, heating of the particles under the laser beam is determined using a thermal analysis, with particle locations determined from the discrete element method simulation. Finally, entrainment of heated powder into the substrate is modelled through a thermal/hydrodynamics coupled model where heat is introduced through a laser ray-tracing module.

While high-fidelity, coupled thermal/hydrodynamic simulations provide the most insight into the build process since they reveal things like pores and the process of powder entrainment, these models are very computationally

intensive, and take on the order of weeks to simulate a small region of built material. To scale the size of simulation up to the part level, we developed a simplified continuum model for simulating the energy and material deposited by the AM process. In this model, we use parameters obtained from both experimental data and the high-fidelity simulation data. The end product of the simulation is a thermal profile, which is then fed into the next stage of our simplified model: a cellular automata finite element code for predicting grain structures.

Fig. 2. (a) Temperature field from a high-fidelity model of the directed energy deposition (DED) process (circle radius is 0.075 cm, 120 Watts laser power, 5 g/min deposition rate, Ti-6Al-4V material); (b) temperature field from a continuum model of the DED process (circle radius is 0.1 cm, 500 Watts laser power, 0.017 g/s deposition rate, 0.0175 m/s scan speed, Ti-6Al-4V material).

Input parameters for the single track continuum DED model include: (1) laser power, (2) laser spot size, (3) laser scan speed, (4) laser wavelength, (5) material deposition rate, and (6) track length. Given these input parameters, the simulation proceeds in the following two stages.

In the first stage, the laser power and spot size are fed into a ray tracing laser source, which introduces energy at the material interface of the void and the substrate. This energy is introduced into the continuum model through a source term, $r(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in (12). The laser advances at the given scan speed on the bare plate, until a steady melt pool width is achieved. The melt pool width, in combination with the material deposition rate and scan speed, are used to compute an ellipsoidal shape of material that is shaped into the domain along the path of the track. Many ellipsoids are shaped along the track, thus approximating a continuous evolution of track shape versus time in the simulation. The height of the shaped ellipsoids are given by the equation

$$c = \frac{24Va}{\pi d(12a^2 - d^2)}, \quad (15)$$

where c is the ellipsoid height from its centroid to its boundary, $V = (\dot{m}\Delta t)/\rho$ is the volume of material to be added by the ellipsoid, \dot{m} is the mass flow rate, Δt is the simulation time between when ellipsoids are shaped in, ρ is the density of the material, a is the ellipsoid width from the centroid to the boundary (matching the melt pool width which can be obtained from laser ray tracing heating and melting a bare plate), and d is the distance between shaped ellipsoids. While powder feed rate is known directly from the DED machine, not all powder particles adhere to the built track. The ratio of the mass flow rate (i.e. adhered material) to the powder feed rate, termed the *capture efficiency*, is affected significantly by the laser power. An approximate relationship between capture efficiency and laser power for Ti-6Al-4V is developed from results reported in Carrozza et al. [36]. This relationship is

$$CE = 0.4044 \log P - 2.042, \quad (16)$$

where CE is the capture efficiency and P is laser power, in Watts. The mass flow rate used in (15) is the product of the capture efficiency given by (16) with the powder flow rate set by the DED machine. Note the capture efficiency is highly dependent on the shielding gas used by the DED machine. The relationship given in (16) assumes an additional flow of argon shielding gas at 15 L/min.

The second stage of the simulation begins with the moving laser source, as with the first stage. Once the laser advances to the width of a shaped ellipsoid, the track (defined by the ellipsoids) begins to be shaped in place. The location of the laser remains at the ellipsoidal front of the track, allowing heat to penetrate the substrate and approximating the non-instantaneous buildup of material along the track. The second stage proceeds until the length of the track has been deposited, at which time the laser is turned off and the ellipsoids are no longer shaped in. The model is allowed to run in the cooling phase until the maximum temperature lowers to beneath melting.

To determine the resulting grain structure of the manufactured part, the temperature profile is fed to cellular automaton (CA) to simulate grain growth. Grain structure provides insight into mechanical properties such as strength, ductility, and isotropy. Dendrite growth is correlated to thermal undercooling and is modeled in the CA using simplified nucleation and growth laws. More details of the CA algorithm can be found in Gandin and Rappaz [37] and Shi et al. [38]. The CA simulations are performed using CAFÉ (Cellular automata finite elements), a module of the ALE3D code (see Appendix B of Khairallah et al. [39]). Figure 3 illustrates a CA grain growth simulation where temperature undercooling is informed by the DED continuum model.

Fig. 3. Microstructure micrograph from CA grain growth simulation with temperature informed from continuum DED simulation (circle radius is 0.1 cm, 300 Watt laser power, 0.0225 m/s scan speed, 0.017 g/s deposition rate, Ti-6Al-4V material).

3.3. Multiple layer continuum model of directed energy deposition

In addition to the single track DED continuum model described above, we also developed a DED continuum model with multiple layers of material deposition, demonstrating a pathway to extend DMD predictions from a single track to part-level predictions. Multi-layer simulations follow much of the same procedure described in Section 3.2, with a few notable exceptions. To ensure a correct deposition rate, the shape of the deposited material is an ellipsoid with the deposited material below subtracted out. This is a consequence of depositing material on a non-smooth surface. Furthermore, the cooling phase between layers is extended to allow heat to dissipate on previous layers before depositing new material. In experiments, interlayer cooldown times of around 5 seconds are common, but for the smaller models utilized in the numerical examples in Section 4, cooldown times of 0.5 seconds were typically sufficient. An example of a wall built up using the continuum DED model is displayed in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Temperature field from a continuum DED simulation of a five layer wall (circle radius is 0.2 cm, 300 Watts laser power, 1 s interlayer cooldown, 0.0225 m/s scan speed, Ti-6Al-4V material).

3.4. Continuum model verification

To ensure the correctness of our continuum model, we simulate the experimental results reported in Carrozza et al. [36] on single tracks of Ti-6Al-4V on a large window of process parameters. We run the model at laser powers of $P \in \{300, 500, 700, 900\}$ W and laser scan speeds of $S \in \{0.01, 0.0125, 0.015, 0.0175, 0.02, 0.0225, 0.025\}$ m/s. The laser spot size is 1 mm and the wavelength is 1070 nm. Powder feed rate from the DED system is 0.017 g/s. To compare the simulation results to the experimental data, we compare the steady state melt pool depths. To obtain a steady melt pool depth measurement, a track length of 0.5 cm is sufficient. The simulated melt pool depths versus those obtained via experimentation (using argon shielding gas) are reported in Figure 5. The model slightly overpredicts melt pool depth at 300 W while slightly underpredicting melt pool depth at 900 W. Predictions match experimentation well for intermediate laser powers. We note experiments were also conducted at 100 W laser power. These resulted in negligible powder adhesion to the base plate. This was replicated in the continuum model, as the predicted melt pool has no width when run at 100 W laser power.

Fig. 5. Predicted melt pool depth versus linear energy density ($LED = P/v$), where P is laser power and v is laser scan speed, for (a) $P = 300 \text{ W}$, (b) $P = 500 \text{ W}$, (c) $P = 700 \text{ W}$, and (d) $P = 900 \text{ W}$ for a single track DED experiment. Simulation results are from the continuum model described in Section 3 and experimental results are reported from Carrozza et al. [36].

4. Numerical simulation results

This section presents four numerical examples which demonstrate different properties of the continuum models and their DMD approximations.

4.1. Reproductive DMD of single track DED

The first example examines the DMD's ability to reproduce the continuum single track DED model. The size of the DMD basis is varied and results using DMD are compared to time windowed DMD. For this simulation, a laser power of 300 W is applied with laser spot size of $D4\sigma = 1 \text{ mm}$ and a laser scan speed of 0.0225 m/s is used. The computational domain is $[0, 8] \text{ mm} \times [0, 3] \text{ mm} \times [-0.7, 0.5] \text{ mm}$ and a regular mesh is used with a resolution of 0.025 mm, resulting in a mesh with 230,400 cuboidal elements and 245,525 degrees of freedom. The substrate is composed of Ti-6Al-4V and occupies $[0, 8] \text{ mm} \times [0, 3] \text{ mm} \times [-0.7, 0] \text{ mm}$ with air filling the balance. An initial temperature of 298.17 K is applied throughout the computational domain. As with the substrate, the DED powder comprises Ti-6Al-4V. A constant powder feed rate of 0.017 g/s is assumed. Along the x -axis, 0.5 cm of material is deposited, resulting in a total simulation time of 222.2 ms, with 5 ms of initial laser dwell time to preheat the substrate and 44.44 ms of cooldown time. The simulation was completed after 2,200 cycles and 32 minutes of wall clock time on 8 cores of an Intel® Xeon® Max 9480 processor. The simulation at 227.2 ms (at the start of the cooldown time) is illustrated in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Single track DED simulation using the continuum model (300 W laser power, 0.0225 m/s laser scan speed, 0.5 cm track length, Ti-6Al-4V material) after 227.2 ms. (a) Top-down view; (b) profile view.

After the initial laser dwell time, snapshots are taken every 0.4444 ms while material is being deposited, resulting in 500 total snapshots during material deposition. These snapshots are used to create two different DMD models: one with no time windowing and one with 5 time windows. Based on the properties of the full-order model solution (smooth and eventually steady state with respect to the location of the laser), there isn't a natural location to introduce time windows in the snapshot data. As a result, we choose to subdivide the snapshots into 5 equal time windows with 2 snapshots of overlap. This gives 102 snapshots in the first four time windows and 100 snapshots in the last window. The performance of the DMD models are evaluated in two different ways: the prediction error versus the size of the DMD basis and the prediction time versus the DMD basis size. These results are summarized in Figure 7. First, the relative prediction error measures the L_2 error in DMD prediction for each of the 500 snapshots taken, i.e.

$$L_2 \text{ error} = \frac{\|\mathbf{u}_{FOM} - \mathbf{u}_{ROM}\|}{\|\mathbf{u}_{FOM}\|}, \quad (17)$$

where \mathbf{u}_{FOM} is snapshot data at t and \mathbf{u}_{ROM} is the DMD prediction at the same time t . Both average and maximum relative prediction error are reported in Figure 7. Average prediction time is the wall clock time taken to predict all snapshots divided by the number of snapshots. Relative basis size is the ratio of DMD basis vectors retained to the total number of basis vectors (i.e. the total number of snapshots). The results indicate both windowed and non-windowed DMD results have a similar relationship between prediction error and relative basis size. Relative L_2 error of approximately 1% can be obtained with 10% of the basis vectors retained. For both DMD models, relative error holds steady at about 0.15% with 40 to 80% of the basis retained. While the introduction of windowing does not affect relative error, it improves the prediction time by about a factor of 10. This is shown in Figure 7b. The savings comes from the reduced size of the DMD matrices that arise from using fewer snapshots when training each time window. Without windowing, the longest DMD prediction time is 0.32 seconds (with 95% of the basis vectors retained) and with windowing, the longest average prediction time is 0.0094 seconds. At 10% of the basis retained, the average prediction time is 0.0027 seconds without windowing and 0.00024 seconds with windowing.

Fig. 7. Error and prediction time for windowed and non-windowed DMD models of the single track DED simulation using the continuum model (300 W laser power, 0.0225 m/s laser scan speed, 0.5 cm track length, Ti-6Al-4V material). (a) Maximum and average relative L_2 prediction error after 67.5 ms versus relative basis size; (b) Average prediction time versus relative basis size.

Finally, the temperature profiles obtained from the full order simulation, the DMD model, and the time windowed DMD model are used to drive a CA grain growth simulation, giving microstructure predictions from each of the three sources. For both the windowed and non-windowed DMD models, 10% of the basis is retained, giving less than 1% average L_2 error in the DMD prediction. Note, the cooling phase must also be modelled for the grain structure prediction to be complete. For both windowed and non-windowed DMD models, the cooling phase is captured in a single window with 50 snapshots and 10 basis vectors retained. The evolution of the temperature field during the cooling phase is captured well by the DMD, as relative L_2 error is small (0.04%) with just 20% of the DMD basis retained. The same CA mesh is used in all three simulations with dimensions of $[0, 8] \text{ mm} \times [1, 2] \text{ mm} \times [-0.25, 0.5] \text{ mm}$ and a mesh resolution of 0.005 mm, giving 33,416,451 zones spread across 1120 domains. Microstructure micrographs of these grain structure predictions along the $x = 3.75 \text{ mm}$ and $y = 1.5 \text{ mm}$ planes are illustrated in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Microstructure micrograph of the single track DED simulation using the continuum model (300 W laser power, 0.0225 m/s laser scan speed, 0.5 cm track length, Ti-6Al-4V material) after 76.36 ms. (a) $y = 1.5$ mm plane of the full order simulation; (b) $x = 2.5$ mm plane of the full order simulation; (c) $y = 1.5$ mm plane of the non-windowed DMD model; (d) $x = 2.5$ mm plane of the non-windowed DMD model; (e) $y = 1.5$ mm plane of the windowed DMD model; (f) $x = 2.5$ mm plane of the windowed DMD model.

4.2. Parametric DMD of single track DED

For this example, the single track continuum DED model is run with 36 different values for laser power ($P \in \{300, 340, 380, 420, 460, 500\}$ W) and scan speed ($S \in \{0.0225, 0.023, 0.0235, 0.024, 0.0245, 0.025\}$ m/s). The parameter values for a specific model run are given by $\mu_j = (P_i, S_i)$ for $j = 1, \dots, 36$, for $P_i \in P$, and for $S_i \in S$. We use a selection of these simulation results (called the training set) to form a parametric DMD, then test the accuracy of this parametric DMD by comparing predicted, interpolated results to simulation results. Since we produce full-order model data at all parameter values, the mesh is coarsened from the previous example to reduce the total runtime required for the full-order simulation. As with the example in Section 4.1, the computational domain for the thermal problem remains $[0, 8] \text{ mm} \times [0, 3] \text{ mm} \times [-0.7, 0.5] \text{ mm}$, but the element size is increased to 0.05 mm giving 230,400 elements and 245,525 degrees of freedom per mesh. Further, the substrate is composed of Ti-6Al-4V and is initially located below the $z = 0$ plane with the remainder of the domain initially filled with air. A single, straight track of Ti-6Al-4V of length 5 mm is placed on the substrate at a constant 0.017 g/s deposition rate. Each analysis requires anywhere from 500 to 1,500 cycles to complete and runs in approximately 15 to 30 minutes of wall clock time on 8 cores of an Intel® Xeon® Max 9480 processor. During the material deposition phase, 100 snapshots of the temperature field are taken from each of the 36 simulations, which are used to develop DMD models of the training set.

The first training set of data selected is at the corners of the parametric domain: $\mu_1 = (300 \text{ W}, 0.0225 \text{ m/s})$, $\mu_6 = (500 \text{ W}, 0.0225 \text{ m/s})$, $\mu_{31} = (300 \text{ W}, 0.025 \text{ m/s})$, and $\mu_{36} = (500 \text{ W}, 0.025 \text{ m/s})$. This represents the smallest set of parameter values that spans the parametric space, enabling interpolation of intermediate points in the domain. For each point in the training set, a DMD model is developed. Error of approximately 3% is targeted for the reproductive DMD case. Based on the improved prediction speed for time windowed DMD, the time windowing approach is used in this example as well. The 100 snapshots are subdivided into 5 time windows with 2 snapshots of overlap, giving 22 snapshots in the first 4 windows and 20 in the final window. Achieving about 3% error required 10 basis vectors per window, for a total of 50 basis vectors over the simulation. The remaining 32 parameter values are added to the test set, meaning DMD models at these values are created by interpolating the DMD models in the training set. The

interpolated models are then compared to available full-order model data for computing error. The interpolation procedure is described in Section A.2. Note, the interpolation procedure there requires the time between snapshots (Δt) remain constant. This is not the case for the different parameter values tested here, which have varying laser scan speeds and, as a result, have different material deposition times. To recover constant Δt , time in all simulations is scaled to that of the lowest laser scan speed, 0.0225 m/s. Additionally, we note the parameter space is mapped to the unit square, such that the radial basis function interpolant does not favor any direction in the parametric space. Finally, we note the capture efficiency is held constant over the 36 simulations, eliminating the change in track height resulting from changes in laser power.

Fig. 9. Relative error for DMD predictions of single track DED simulations using the continuum model over a range of laser powers and scan speeds. Values with bold borders represent data in the training set, while DMD models at other parameter values are generated through interpolation of training data. (a) Relative L_2 prediction error at the last snapshot time with a training set size of 4; (b) Relative L_2 prediction error at the last snapshot time with a greedily sampled training set size of 6.

In Figure 9a, L_2 relative prediction error at the last snapshot for all 36 models is presented. In this figure, bolded square outlines represent data in the training set, while non-bolded outlines represent DMD models created by interpolation of the training set. As the figure illustrates, error in the interpolation of the laser power is higher than the error in interpolation of the laser scan speed. This suggests that additional refinement is required along the laser power axis. In general, changes to laser scan speed are expected to produce larger changes to the underlying model. The reasoning is twofold. First, changes in laser scan speed change the shape of the deposited material to maintain the constant material deposition rate. Second, the time scaling required to maintain constant Δt results in diffusion of laser energy occurring at different rates, leading to larger differences in the full order model data at different scan speeds. However, the range of laser scan speeds used in this parametric study is small enough to counteract these effects. Error at parameter values in the training set tops out at 3.12% at $\mu_1 = (300 \text{ W}, 0.0225 \text{ m/s})$, while the interpolated DMD model error is a maximum at $\mu_3 = (380 \text{ W}, 0.0225 \text{ m/s})$ (16.8%).

Since full-order model data is available at all the points in parametric space tested, additional parameter points can be added to the training set with the goal of reducing the prediction error over the range of scan speeds and laser powers tested. We note this process can be done without full-order model data available using error indicators [40] and uncertainty quantification [41] as a proxy for error calculations. However, since full-order model data is available for this example, we can evaluate error directly and introduce more parameter points into the parametric DMD model where error is largest – a process called greedy sampling. This process is carried out until the largest relative prediction error over the parametric space is reduced below 10%, which necessitated adding two additional parameter values to the training set: $\mu_3 = (380 \text{ W}, 0.0225 \text{ m/s})$ and $\mu_{33} = (380 \text{ W}, 0.025 \text{ m/s})$. The prediction error over the parametric space with the additional sampled parameter values is illustrated in Figure 9b. With the new data in the

training set, the maximum error is reduced to 8.56%. The spatial distribution of error for this case is illustrated in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Spatial distribution of relative error from using an interpolated DMD to predict temperature in a single track DED simulation using the continuum model (380 W laser power, 0.0225 m/s laser scan speed, 0.5 cm track length, Ti-6Al-4V material) at 0.038 ms, the time with the largest relative error. (a) Top-down view; (b) profile view.

4.3. Parametric DMD of multiple layer DED

In the final example, we develop a parametric DMD for predicting the thermal profile of a multi-layer wall printed using DED. As with the example in Section 4.2, we use parametric DMD to predict thermal fields at arbitrary values of laser scan speed and laser power over a parametric domain. We choose to develop the DMD model layer-by-layer, which helps generalize the resulting model, but leads to a couple of complications in its development. The first complication is ensuring that the DMD snapshots for each layer roughly contain the same track geometry, meaning the track begins and ends at the same point in the model snapshot and the time required to lay down the track is the same, regardless of scan speed. This is handled by computing the DMD over a subdomain of the entire computational domain. This subdomain is centered on the track currently being laid and has an affine transformation applied to time and space domains such that the track begins and ends at the same time and location in all DMD subdomains. This simplifies parametric interpolation of the DMD solutions, ensuring variation from DMD model to DMD model is minimal. However, DMD prediction is only possible in the subdomain, leaving the temperature field outside the subdomain unchanged. Note, this will not influence the resulting grain structure predicted by CA, provided there is sufficient cooling time in the DMD model for the track to solidify. The second complication is including the temperature effects of previously laid tracks. This is simplified by including a proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) of the initial conditions as an additional parameter, which is used to weight the value of each of the DMD models from each layer in the training data. If the layer appears in the training data, then the POD ensures it is used to generate the DMD prediction. If a layer has not appeared, then the POD constructs a linear combination of the layers in the training data that best match the initial conditions observed.

The parameters of the continuum model closely follow the parameters of the previous two examples: 5 mm tracks of Ti-6Al-4V are laid upon a Ti-6Al-4V substrate. However, in this example, 5 tracks are laid on top of each other, resulting in a small wall of built-up material. The overall modelling domain is larger in this example to accommodate the additional layers: $[0, 8] \text{ mm} \times [0, 3] \text{ mm} \times [-0.7, 1.0] \text{ mm}$. Besides simulating material deposition, each model includes 5 ms of initial laser dwell time to preheat the substrate and 1 s of inter-layer cooling time. The element length remains 0.05 mm as in the example in Section 4.2, giving a total of 224,000 elements and 236,985 degrees of freedom. A short description of the DMD model generation procedure follows.

1. Produce full order model data for the multi-layer wall at different parameter values where you wish to build the initial training set. For this example, those values are $\mu_1 = (300 \text{ W}, 0.024 \text{ m/s})$, $\mu_3 = (380 \text{ W}, 0.024 \text{ m/s})$, $\mu_7 = (300 \text{ W}, 0.025 \text{ m/s})$, and $\mu_9 = (380 \text{ W}, 0.025 \text{ m/s})$.
2. Build the subdomain of each layer and save snapshots, ensuring the position of the track and time length to lay the track is consistent among all layers and parameter values. In this example, we choose to use 500 snapshots of the deposition process and 50 snapshots of the cooling process per subdomain.
3. Train a DMD of each track of each parameter in the training set. As with the previous example, the basis retained is 10% of the number of total snapshots during the deposition process and 20% of the total snapshots during cooling.
4. Choose parameter values for the test set, then compute interpolated DMD models at these points, using the RBF interpolation of the tangent space to the manifold of the DMD basis, as described in Section A.2. Test set values in this example are $\mu_2 = (340 \text{ W}, 0.024 \text{ m/s})$, $\mu_4 = (300 \text{ W}, 0.0245 \text{ m/s})$, $\mu_5 = (340 \text{ W}, 0.0245 \text{ m/s})$, $\mu_6 = (380 \text{ W}, 0.0245 \text{ m/s})$, and $\mu_8 = (340 \text{ W}, 0.025 \text{ m/s})$.
5. Using the interpolated DMD models, compute initial DMD predictions for each track available. Compute the POD of the initial prediction for each track to complete definition of the DMD model.

With the DMD model at all points in the test set, prediction proceeds by generating DMD predictions for each layer available in the test set, then using the POD to generate a linear combination of layer contributions given the initial conditions of the predicted DMD model.

Relative errors in the DMD prediction for the last snapshot of the first (bottom) layer and the fifth (top) layer are illustrated in Figure 11. Prediction error largely mirrors the parametric example in Section 4.2: interpolation over laser power gives minimal error as compared to interpolating over laser scan speed. For the reproductive DMDs at the corners of the parametric domain, error remains around 1% for the first track. However, as the number of layers increases, the error increases as well, for both reproductive DMDs and interpolated DMDs. Error accumulation is likely attributed to using the final DMD prediction for the previous layer as the initial condition for the next layer. Since the initial conditions for each track do not precisely match the conditions at the end of the previous track due to error in DMD prediction, the linear combination of track data predicted by the POD likely includes small contributions from other layers, increasing the prediction error. Nevertheless, the L_2 relative prediction error remains a manageable 15.0% at worst. This can likely be reduced through the addition of more parameter values in the test set.

Fig. 11. Relative error for DMD predictions of multi-layer DED simulations using the continuum model over a range of laser powers and scan speeds. Values with bold borders represent data in the training set, while DMD models at other parameter values are generated through interpolation of training data. (a) Relative L_2 prediction error at the last snapshot time over layer 1; (b) Relative L_2 prediction error at the last snapshot time over layer 5.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we demonstrated dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) as a capable tool for predicting results of a continuum model of directed energy deposition (DED). The continuum model is one piece of a basic framework, which takes DED machine parameters and a tool path as inputs and ends with a prediction of the microstructure of a printed part. Computing the thermal profile during the deposition process is a significant portion of the total run time of the simulation when a full-order model is required. With DMD, the time required generating thermal profiles is nearly instantaneous, removing a bottleneck in the pipeline. Even with the refined models presented in Section 4.1, DMD enables prediction of the thermal field at around 1% error in under a millisecond.

While the standard DMD model performs admirably, we apply several enhancements to the DMD framework which enable faster performance and parametric predictions. The first enhancement is a windowing approach described in Cheung et al. [32] which subdivides the snapshots into several, smaller DMD submodels. This leads to multiple benefits. First, the range of prediction for each DMD submodel can be shrunk to where the dynamics can be better approximated by a linear operator. This allows for more compression of the DMD without losing any accuracy. Also, by reducing the number of snapshots in each DMD submodel, the size of the basis and operators can be reduced, which can significantly reduce the time required to generate predictions. In the example in Section 4.1, introducing 5 time windows leads to a speedup of about 10x in prediction time. The other enhancement is a technique for interpolation of a parametric solution manifold introduced in Choi et al. [33] in the context of projection-based reduced order models. In Section 4.2, the example demonstrates this method works capably for parametric interpolation of DMD models as well. Coupled with a greedy sampling algorithm, radial basis function interpolation of DMD models over the parametric space gives prediction errors of under 10% with nearly instantaneous prediction times.

Beyond single track simulations, the framework also extends to multiple layers of material deposition. With multiple layers, there are some complicating factors. First, the position of each track must be the same with respect to the DMD model. In the example in Section 4.3, this is handled by generating a subdomain over which snapshots are recorded and the DMD is actively predicting. Each subdomain is mirrored and reflected as necessary such that the track begins and ends at the same relative position in the DMD model. Also, initial conditions of the temperature field are complicated by laser heat introduced during the deposition of previous layers. For the multi-layer wall structure presented in Section 4.3, the initial conditions are compressed using a proper orthogonal decomposition, allowing the initial conditions for subsequent layers to be expressed as a linear combination of the previous layers. With these enhancements, a DMD model of a multi-layer part is demonstrated in Section 4.3 giving near instantaneous prediction and relatively small error for the reproductive case (less than 5%).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Eric B. Chin: Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – Original Draft, Visualization. **Saad Khairallah:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Youngsoo Choi:** Methodology, Software, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision. **Arlie Capps:** Software, Validation. **Joseph T. McKeown:** Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Enhancements to dynamic mode decomposition

A.1. Time windowing dynamic mode decomposition

With slow decay in the Kolmogorov n -width, the number of retained DMD modes, r , grows for a desired DMD accuracy. This situation occurs when the underlying snapshot data is not largely linearly dependent and, therefore, cannot be represented using a low-dimensional subspace. With a larger number of modes retained to achieve the desired accuracy, the size of the reduced operator increases and DMD training and prediction times increase. For a certain class of problems, linear dependence of the snapshot data can be improved by subdividing the snapshots into subsets. Cheung et al. [32] demonstrated this for a shock-induced pore collapse simulation, where each subset of snapshots, termed a *window* of the snapshot data, is determined by either the time passed in the simulation (time windowing) or a distance measure corresponding to the location of the primary shock (distance windowing). While the applicability of the windowing technique is dependent on the snapshot data used, for the simulation data used in this manuscript, time windowing proved adequate for realizing the benefits of windowing.

Formally, given a set of N snapshots equally spaced in time, choose a set of positive integers $\{N_1, \dots, N_n\}$ such that $N_{i+1} > N_i$ and $N_n = N$. These integers correspond to the subdivision of the snapshots into windows where the size of window $1 < i < n$ is $N_i - N_{i-1} + 1$ where $N_0 = 1$. The size of each window should be chosen such that the decay of the Kolmogorov n -width is maximized over the windows. In practice, this means the data in each window should be able to be represented by a small ($r_i \ll N_i$) set of DMD basis vectors. We also define a set of positive integers $\{o_2, \dots, o_n\}$ which define the size of the overlap on each window. Over each window, the procedure described in Section 2.1 should be largely followed. Instead of constructing an operator over all snapshots, we wish to form a linear operator A_i for $i = 1, \dots, n$ which predicts how the dynamical system evolves over the window. Forming the matrices

$$U_i^- = [\mathbf{u}_{N_{i-1}-o_i} \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{u}_{N_i-1}] \quad \text{and} \quad U_i^+ = [\mathbf{u}_{N_{i-1}-o_i-1} \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{u}_{N_i}]. \quad (18)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, n$ where $N_0 = 1$ and $o_1 = 0$, the reduced linear operator can be approximated by the reduced SVD of $U_i^- \approx W_i \Sigma_i V_i^T$ where $W_i \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times r_i}$, $\Sigma_i \in \mathbb{R}^{r_i \times r_i}$, and $V_i \in \mathbb{R}^{(N_i+o_i) \times r_i}$:

$$\tilde{A}_i \approx W_i^T U_i^+ V_i \Sigma_i^{-1}. \quad (19)$$

The eigendecomposition of the reduced operator is $\tilde{A}_i = X_i \Lambda_i X_i^{-1}$ where $X_i \in \mathbb{C}^{r_i \times r_i}$ is a matrix whose columns hold the eigenvectors of \tilde{A}_i and $\Lambda_i \in \mathbb{C}^{r_i \times r_i}$ is a diagonal matrix holding eigenvalues. Finally, the prediction over time window i is given by

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \Phi_i \Lambda_i^{\frac{t-t_{i-1}+o_i \Delta t}{\Delta t}} \Phi_i^* \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i \quad \text{for } t \in [t_{i-1}, t_i], \quad (20)$$

where t_i is the time of snapshot N_i , $t_0 = 0$, and $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i$ is defined recursively using $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_1 = \mathbf{u}_1$ and

Fig. 12. Summary of the time-windowing dynamic mode decomposition algorithm.

$$\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i = \Phi_{i-1} \Lambda_{i-1}^{\frac{t_{i-1}-o_i \Delta t}{\Delta t}} \Phi_{i-1}^* \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{i-1}. \quad (21)$$

The time windowing algorithm is summarized in Figure 12.

A.2. Parametric dynamic mode decomposition

The DMD techniques described above are useful for compressing and reproducing existing simulation data, a scenario called the *reproductive* case. More useful in this context is *predictive* DMD, where the simulation results of some parameter values that have not been calculated are predicted. To enable predictive DMD, a method of taking existing DMDs at known parameter values and interpolating them at arbitrary parameter values is needed. Several methods for parametric interpolation of DMD simulations are in the open literature, such as the ones described in Huhn et al. [29] and in Choi et al. [33]. In Huhn et al. [29], two novel approaches for interpolation are devised: one based on the interpolation of the reduced-order DMD eigenpair and a second based on the interpolation of the reduced DMD operator. In Choi et al. [33], a more general framework for interpolating a parametric solution manifold is introduced, which uses radial basis function interpolation of existing trained DMD models at a new parametric value of the DMD where data does not exist. In this manuscript, we employ the second approach.

Given a set of m DMD solutions $\{D_1, \dots, D_m\}$ with parameter values $P = \{\boldsymbol{\mu}_1, \dots, \boldsymbol{\mu}_m\}$ where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is a vector of parameter values, we wish to compute $D(\boldsymbol{\mu})$, the predicted DMD solution for parameter value $\boldsymbol{\mu} \in \mathbb{R}^p$. For all the DMD solutions, we require the same number of snapshots, the same (constant) timestep, Δt , and the same reduced basis size r . The interpolated DMD solution at $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is of the form given in (11), meaning the DMD basis \mathbf{W} and the reduced linear operator $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ must be interpolated. The SVD of the solution with parameter value $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ in general will have a different basis than the SVD of the solution with parameter value $\boldsymbol{\mu}_j$ when $i \neq j$. As a result, the basis of each DMD solution must be rotated such that the interpolation is performed in the same basis. To perform basis rotation, a reference basis, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_0 = \boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ is first selected and all other DMD solutions are rotated in terms of the reference basis. The reference basis is chosen as the set of parameter values $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ which minimizes the L_2 distance from $\boldsymbol{\mu}$:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_0 = \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\mu}_i \in P} ((\boldsymbol{\mu}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}) \cdot (\boldsymbol{\mu}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}))^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (22)$$

The solution of the orthogonal Procrustes problem gives an orthogonal matrix $\mathbf{Q}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ relating the two bases. Note that while multiplying the basis by an orthogonal matrix changes the basis vectors, it does not change the subspace which the basis represents. In other words, modifying the DMD basis \mathbf{W} and reduced linear operator $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$

associated with D_i through the orthogonal matrix \mathbf{Q}_i does not change the underlying DMD solution, only the basis vectors which represent that solution. The solution of the orthogonal Procrustes problem is

$$\mathbf{Q}_i = \mathbf{U}_i \mathbf{Z}_i^T, \quad (23)$$

where \mathbf{U}_i and \mathbf{Z}_i come from the SVD of $\mathbf{W}_i^T \mathbf{W}_0 = \mathbf{U}_i \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i \mathbf{Z}_i^T$, where \mathbf{W}_i is the DMD basis of D_i and \mathbf{W}_0 is the DMD basis for reference parameter values $\boldsymbol{\mu}_0$. With the matrix \mathbf{Q}_i , the rotated DMD basis and reduced linear operators are given by

$$\mathbf{W}_i^R = \mathbf{W}_i \mathbf{Q}_i \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i^R = \mathbf{Q}_i^T \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i \mathbf{Q}_i, \quad (24)$$

respectively, where $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i$ is the reduced linear operator for D_i .

Interpolation of the rotated matrices is simplified by first projecting the matrix manifold of the matrices to a vector space, where any multi-variate interpolant valid on vector spaces can be applied. Such a vector space is given by the tangent space to the matrix manifold at a point and a mapping from (to, resp.) the matrix manifold to (from, resp.) its tangent at a reference point is given by the logarithmic (exponential, resp.) map. Given a reference point on the matrix manifold, $\mathbf{W}_0 \in \mathcal{M}_W$, where \mathcal{M}_W is the matrix manifold of the DMD basis, we define the logarithmic map at nearby point \mathbf{W}_i^R as $\Gamma_i^W = \text{Log}_{\mathbf{W}_0} \mathbf{W}_i^R$ and similarly, given $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_0 \in \mathcal{M}_A$, a reference point on \mathcal{M}_A with parameter values $\boldsymbol{\mu}_0$, the matrix manifold of the DMD reduced linear operators, the logarithmic map at nearby point $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i^R$ is defined to be $\Gamma_i^A = \text{Log}_{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_0} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i^R$. A point on the matrix manifold is considered nearby if it lies within the neighborhood of \mathbf{W}_0 or $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_0$ where the logarithmic map exists and is unique. The exponential (inverse) maps are simply $\text{Exp}_{\mathbf{W}_0} \Gamma_i^W$, where Γ_i^W is a point on the vector space tangent to the point \mathbf{W}_0 on the matrix manifold \mathcal{M}_W , or $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{W}_0} \mathcal{M}_W$, and $\text{Exp}_{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_0} \Gamma_i^A$, where Γ_i^A is a point on $\mathcal{T}_{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_0} \mathcal{M}_A$.

Different exponential and logarithmic matrix mappings exist depending on the algebraic properties of the matrix one hopes to retain. For further details, see Amsallem and Farhat [42]. To map the DMD basis, a rectangular matrix, the following mapping is used

$$\Gamma_i^W = \text{Log}_{\mathbf{W}_0} \mathbf{W}_i^R = \mathbf{W}_i^R - \mathbf{W}_0 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Exp}_{\mathbf{W}_0} \Gamma_i^W = \mathbf{W}_0 + \Gamma_i^W, \quad (25)$$

and similarly, for the reduced linear operator, the mapping is

$$\Gamma_i^A = \text{Log}_{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_0} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i^R = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i^R - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_0 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Exp}_{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_0} \Gamma_i^A = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_0 + \Gamma_i^A. \quad (26)$$

Interpolation of the logarithmically mapped quantities is performed using radial basis function (RBF) interpolation. An RBF is radial in the sense its value only depends on its (typically Euclidian) distance from a point. When RBFs are used as an interpolant, the center point for each basis function coincides with known values of some function, and the RBFs are used to weight contributions from different points. Commonly used RBFs include Gaussian, $\varphi(\rho) = \exp(-\epsilon\rho)$, inverse quadratic, $\varphi(\rho) = (1 + (\epsilon\rho)^2)^{-1}$, and inverse multiquadric, $\varphi(\boldsymbol{\mu}) = (1 + (\epsilon\rho)^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, where ϵ is a shape parameter and $\rho = \|\boldsymbol{\mu} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_c\|$ is the Euclidean distance from $\boldsymbol{\mu}_c$, the center point. These RBFs are positive definite and from C^∞ , but do not have the compact support property (i.e., they are non-zero everywhere). An RBF interpolant of a matrix $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}$ over the m DMD solutions is formed using the following expression

$$\boldsymbol{\Gamma}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) = \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i \varphi(\|\boldsymbol{\mu} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_i\|), \quad (27)$$

Fig. 13. Overview of the parametric DMD algorithm presented in Choi et al. [33].

where λ_i is a matrix weight determined by the solution of the following linear system of equations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varphi(\|\mu_1 - \mu_1\|) & \cdots & \varphi(\|\mu_m - \mu_1\|) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \varphi(\|\mu_1 - \mu_m\|) & \cdots & \varphi(\|\mu_m - \mu_m\|) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} (\lambda_0)_{ij} \\ \vdots \\ (\lambda_m)_{ij} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (\Gamma(\mu_1))_{ij} \\ \vdots \\ (\Gamma(\mu_m))_{ij} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (28)$$

where $(\lambda_k)_{ij}$ and $(\Gamma(\mu_k))_{ij}$ correspond to row i and column j of λ_k and $\Gamma(\mu_k)$, respectively, for $k = 1, \dots, m$ and $\Gamma(\mu_k) = \Gamma_k$, the (known) matrix at parameter value μ_k .

To summarize, the steps of the parametric DMD algorithm are as follows (also see Figure 13). Given m DMD reduced order models, $\{D_1, \dots, D_m\}$, with parameter values $P = \{\mu_1, \dots, \mu_m\}$ and a point in parameter space μ where we would like to approximate the DMD solution, compute the following:

1. Find the nearest parameter in the set P to μ in an L_2 sense using (22). Call this parameter value μ_0 and the associated DMD solution D_0 . We also refer to the matrix holding the DMD basis for D_0 as W_0 and the reduced linear operator for D_0 as \tilde{A}_0 .
2. For every parameter value in $P \setminus \mu$, for the corresponding DMD solution D_i find the rotated DMD basis W_i^R and rotated reduced linear operator \tilde{A}_i^R using (23) and (24).
3. Project each rotated basis and reduced linear operator matrix, W_i^R and \tilde{A}_i^R , respectively, for $i = 1, \dots, m$ to the tangent space of the matrix manifold using the logarithmic maps in (25) and (26). These projected matrices are Γ_i^W and Γ_i^A .
4. Use (27) to find the RBF interpolation of the projected matrices at μ .
5. Map the interpolated projected matrix back to the matrix manifold using the exponential maps in (25) and (26). This gives the interpolated DMD matrices W and \tilde{A} , which define the interpolated DMD solution at μ .

Note the interpolation algorithm is also compatible with the time windowing approach, provided the windows are coincident for all parameter values.

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